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An Overview of Mobility Management mechanisms and its challenges in 5G and Beyond networks

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NOKIA

Agenda

1. Mobility Management
2. Challenges
3. Future works
4. Conclusion

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Mobility Management in 5G networks and beyond

- One of the **primary features** of wireless networks
- Required to ensure:
 - ✓ Network can “**reach**” the user
 - ✓ User can “**initiate**” communication
 - ✓ connectivity “**Maintained**” as the user moves

- eMBB
 - mMTC
 - URLLC
- } require different **QoS**

Mobility Management Mechanisms should be **ADAPTED** and **IMPROVED** to ensure the required **QoS** and seamless mobility in future networks!

Mobility Management in 5G networks and beyond

HANDOVER process:

- Measurement Report
- Handover Request
- Handover Request Acknowledge

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Mobility Management in 5G networks and beyond

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- UE has Handed-over to the Target Cell

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Challenges

- mmWaves and **Small Cells** deployment
- **High-speed** mobility

Important Performance Parameter:

- Frequent **HOs**
- HO failure **HOF**
- Radio Link failure **RLF**
- Ping-Pong effects **PP**

Challenges

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- Network complexity and **Densification (UDN)**

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- Dual connectivity (**DC**)

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Challenges

- mmWaves and **Small Cells** deployment
- **High-speed** mobility
- Network complexity and Densification (**UDN**)
- Dual connectivity (**DC**)
- **Beam level** management

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Future works

- The study will be focused on finding better solutions for **Mobility Management techniques** with ability to overcome the challenges by handling many scenarios that the users might experience in different network densifications at different times.
- Utilizing **Context Awareness** techniques will ensure the consideration of user, network, and application context conditions while selecting the appropriate MM solution when it's needed
- Many **Machine Learning** techniques can help predict/estimate valuable system parameters (such as **RSRP, RSRQ, user location, user speed, user direction** and **load condition**, etc.) to avoid the frequent **HOs, PP, HOF, and RLF probabilities** by selecting appropriate HO method and time to trigger the HO process.

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Conclusion

This review paper highlighted the importance of **Mobility Management** and its challenges in the current and future wireless networks. Therefore, according to the complexity of the wireless networks, A review of the **Mobility Management** mechanisms with their capabilities, and persistent challenges will assist to design better **Mobility Management** strategies to improve the **network performance** and **user experience**.

Also, the many possible scenarios in future networks appear the many queries on Mobility Management mechanisms that can be actively checked by the research and industrial communities.

THANK YOU
FOR YOUR ATTENTION

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